

PEDAGOGICAL CONTENT OF SPIRITUAL AND MORAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS THROUGH MUSIC

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Annotation: This article is aimed at studying the educational power of music, analyzing its spiritual and moral impact on students, and demonstrating the pedagogical foundations of developing moral qualities through musical activity. The article discusses the role and significance of musical instruments in the social, spiritual and moral development of the younger generation, as well as its effective use in musical pedagogical processes.

Keywords: spiritual and moral education, pedagogical activity, pedagogical characteristics, musical instrument, student, musical activity, pedagogical content.

The art of music is of great importance in educating students not only aesthetically, but also spiritually and morally. Through music lessons and musical activities, it is possible to form in students such moral principles as good behavior, culture, respect for national and universal values. The influence of music on spiritual education is great and very important. Music not only improves the mental state of a person, but also has a positive effect on his spiritual and moral development. The influence of music on spiritual education is manifested in spiritual and emotional development, in the formation of moral values, in the expansion of aesthetic worldview, and in the strengthening of human qualities.

Musical instruments express and enrich a person's spiritual state. Properly selected musical works help a person develop spiritually, change his emotions. Through music, a person understands himself, understands his inner world, and often receives deep emotional experiences.

Music can teach life's moral lessons. Many types of music, especially folk music, promote values such as justice, honesty, kindness, and patience. Through music, people can learn and practice moral behavior.

Through music, one can understand and appreciate art and beauty, and broaden one's worldview. At the same time, a musical instrument develops qualities such as determination, patience, and self-control. Learning music, learning to play musical works, often requires time and effort, which teaches students to strive for goals, work on themselves, and be diligent.

LITERATURE ANALYSIS AND METHODOLOGY.

Music develops mutual understanding, respect, and cooperation between people in society. Group musical activities, such as working in an orchestra or choir,

teach people to work as a team, strengthen the spirit of joint creation and achievement. Thus, music becomes an integral part of spiritual education. The role of music is not only to express emotions, but also plays a major role in the moral, aesthetic, and spiritual development of a person.

If we look at music as a means of education, it is a force that reflects and awakens all educational signs in one. In this sense, “Good manners, good manners, gentleness and nobility are among the true signs of education,” writes scholar G’aybulla as-Salom [5]. Along with these experiences, certain spiritual and aesthetic thoughts also arise. According to B.M. Teplov, another important thing in artistic education is that “work” in one art form can contribute to the formation of artistic abilities in other types of art [8].

One of the Eastern thinkers, Al-Biruni, described in his works that it is possible to implement spiritual and moral education through music. His contemporary, the scholar Abu Ali Ibn Sina, known as “Shaykh-ur-Rais”, expresses his musical views by linking them with morality. Ibn Sina, in his works “Donishnama” and “Kitab Ush-Shifo”, specifically focuses on the art of music and musical performance [9]. In particular, the fourth part of “Donishnama”, dedicated to the art of music, extensively covers the characteristics of musical sounds and instrumental melodies. In “Kitab Ush-Shifo”, Ibn Sina also discusses the spiritual and moral educational properties of the art of music.

The most significant work in the development of aesthetic thought is the “Qabusnama”. Kaykovus (1021-1098) made a great contribution to the enrichment of the spiritual world of humanity and the development of aesthetic thought through this work. In the “Qabusnama”, which Kaykovus dedicated to his son Gilanshah, the goal of educating humanity in the world of spirituality, elegance and beauty, and the importance of the art of music in becoming a perfect person in society was explained in detail in this work [9].

DISCUSSION. Music is the oldest and greatest art of mankind, which not only gives aesthetic pleasure and understanding, but also has the power to influence the human psyche. Music also shows its great importance as a means of moral and spiritual education. Through music education, students can be taught not only aesthetic beauty, but also social values, moral principles and spiritual values. In the modern education system of Uzbekistan, the educational aspects of music are seen as an important tool, especially serving the spiritual and moral development of students.

Spiritual and moral education through music is an important part of the pedagogical process. Spiritual and moral education is teaching a person to choose the right path in life, to make moral decisions in a social environment. It is very

important for students to understand this role of music, to connect it with the processes of personal development and social integration.

Music reflects various social and moral values, such as honesty, hard work, solidarity, patriotism, and humanity. During music lessons, students learn to understand and appreciate the rich cultural heritage of the Uzbek people more deeply by learning about the musical traditions of different peoples, the musical art of their own nation, and its history [7].

In music lessons, students experience a variety of emotions through musical works. This process plays a major role in shaping their emotional and spiritual world. Through music, students understand their inner world and through this, they develop moral qualities such as understanding themselves and those around them, understanding others, showing compassion and respect for them.

RESULTS. The pedagogical features of the spiritual and moral education of students through music are manifested in the following processes:

1. Through musical works, they learn to understand and feel the feelings of other people. For example, listening to songs or musical works and giving in to emotions through them contributes to the development of the student's personality [6].

2. Music lessons teach how to communicate with others in a social environment and show respect for them, and work together.

3. When teaching music, difficult but necessary ethical questions arise for students, such as understanding the value of labor, ensuring justice, and making correct and impartial decisions.

The art of music is closely connected with the spiritual values of the Uzbek people. Uzbek music, folk songs, melodies and paintings preserve within themselves the unique form of national heritage, traditions and historical values. By introducing students to this heritage, their national consciousness develops, a sense of national pride and patriotism is formed. Through music, acquaintance with national and universal values, understanding the history, culture and literature of the Uzbek people, teaches young people to feel responsible for their nation.

A number of pedagogical methods and techniques can be effectively used in providing spiritual and moral education in music education. By analyzing musical works, listening to musical works, and analyzing their content, students understand moral problems and social issues. Group work: through the activities of ensembles, choirs, and orchestras, students learn to help each other and work together. Musical improvisation and performance: teaching students to express their feelings through musical expressions deepens the importance of music for them. Spiritual and moral education of students through music, as an integral part of the pedagogical process, plays an important role in the formation of the younger generation. Music teaches

students to develop moral values, to respect social responsibility, culture, and universal values. This process shows that music education is aimed at developing not only aesthetic, but also moral and spiritual aspects. Thus, educating students through music contributes not only to the art of music, but also to their personal and social development.

In this way, spiritual and moral education directs a person to spiritual development and moral responsibility, which helps him find his place in society and make positive changes.

CONCLUSION. Speaking about the pedagogical features of spiritual and moral education of students through music, the art of music serves as an effective means of providing students with not only aesthetic, but also moral and spiritual education. The main goal of music pedagogy is to develop the personality of students, teach them human values, and ensure physical and mental health [4].

Music, through its lyrical features, rhythmic and melodic structure, forms emotional and moral concepts in students. Music, influencing a person's inner world, expands his spiritual scope, helps to understand himself and others. Through music, a student learns not only culture, but also social responsibility.

Through music, students are instilled with the concepts of right and wrong, good and bad. Through the images and plots in musical works, it helps a person to accept high moral values such as goodness, kindness, sincerity, patriotism.

Music lessons, in particular, develop the personal aspects of the student. In the process of performing or listening to music, the student increases his creative potential and develops self-confidence. This forms moral qualities, responsibility and mutual respect.

Through music lessons, students learn to work together in a group, teamwork, social cooperation. Through music, they are educated to establish balanced and respectful relationships with others in the community. Through music, students learn national culture, traditions and values. This, in turn, fosters in them a sense of love for their homeland and respect for their ancestors

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